

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ:
ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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THE NEED FOR INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS
TEACHERS

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Abstract: *This article contains opinions about the ways, methods and necessity of preparing future primary school teachers for innovative activities, as well as the modern stages of the development of the educational system.*

With the development and progress of the new Uzbekistan, the demand and needs for highly qualified editors are increasing day by day. In particular, he has the ability to educate a mature generation in the spirit of universal and national values that have been formed over the centuries, he has mastered the fundamentals of science, the methods of editorial and psychology science, he has a high level of professional competence, and he has the ability to apply modern editorial and information technologies in practice. a skilled artist editors are required.

In the process of higher editorial education, there is an opportunity to form a student personality who can meet these requirements and has quality skills. For this, there is a growing demand for the wide use of modern innovations and innovations in the process of higher educational education aimed at training future primary school teachers. The effectiveness of innovative editorial activity is determined by the personality of the editor.

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One of the most important issues in innovative editorial activity is the personality of the teacher.

The future teacher should be an innovative, productive creative person, should have creativity, wide-ranging interest and training, inner world, and editorial skills.

The training of the future elementary school teacher for innovative editorial activity should be carried out in two directions:

- formation of innovative enthusiasm for the perception of time;
- teach to be able to act on it.

Educational and cognitive activity of the future teacher and its management are of special importance in the organization of innovative editorial activity.

Studying the editorial bases of innovation processes, their functions, development laws, mechanisms and technologies of their implementation, management principles allows to organize the educational process of the higher school at the level of world standards based on the achievements of modern editorial and psychology sciences.

There are no special methods in society that force a person to stop his innovative activity. It is very important for a future teacher to feel, experience and get rid of psychological obstacles that prevent him from carrying out innovative educational activity in the future. Innovative behavior is not flexibility, but individuality, self-activation, maximum development of systematization. If someone has given up some of his values and ideals, violated his moral and intellectual integrity, became unhappy, lost his freedom, the teacher should be able to mentally enter his mind and feel him. Ibn Sina enumerates a number of moral qualities of a person's behavior and analyzes their impact on a person's soul from a redagogical-psychological point of view. For example, he described generosity as a human power that helps people in need, humility as a power that prevents selfishness, friendship as a source of mutual care and cooperation.

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The necessary component in the training structure of future elementary school teachers is their professional ability to implement innovative educational activities, and it is determined by specific criteria. The ability of an editor for any profession, including the ability to engage in innovative editorial activity, can be expressed by the following symbolic formula:

Each period of the development of the educational system is characterized by its own innovative educational goals, which are internal and external to the dominant goal of this period. In the higher educational system, there were innovative ideas such as programmed learning, problem-based learning, modular learning, codified learning, and others.

At the modern stage of the development of the educational system of Uzbekistan, the following *editorial ideas are innovative*:

- personalized training;
- humanization and humanity of education;
- credit system of education;
- technologicalization of the educational process;
- computerization of the educational process;
- introducing the ideas of Uzbek folk pedagogy into the educational process;
- quality management of the education system;
- didactic foundations of the educational system.

Common signs of a teacher's ability to implement editorial tasks can be the following:

- to be able to model the editor's expected communication with the audience in the process of engaging in direct activity with students;
- the ability to see each of his actions through the eyes of the students, the ability to determine how the contents and results of his editorial actions are reflected in the minds and views of the students, and the desire to do so;

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- the emotional unity of the teacher and the students, this allows the teacher to foresee the situation expected in the lesson, to feel the level of interaction that can be expected during the lesson, and to develop it in the future;
- the ability to add the subjective experience of each student to the educational process;
- the ability to understand the point of view of a colleague and at the same time to be ambitious, demanding, etc. in a team.

The above pre-determines the pedagogical views of the teacher, which help to determine whether or not he is able to implement innovative activity directed at the student's personality.

The general signs of the future elementary school ***teacher's ability to implement the above-mentioned pedagogical tasks*** may be the following:

- to be able to model the editor's expected communication with the audience in the process of engaging in direct activity with students;
- the ability to see each of his actions through the eyes of the students, the ability to determine how the contents and results of his editorial actions are reflected in the minds and views of the students, and the desire to do so;
- the emotional unity of the teacher and the students, which allows the teacher to foresee the situation expected in the lesson, to feel the level of interaction that can be expected in the course of the lesson, and to encourage it to develop in the future;
- the ability to add the subjective experience of each student to the educational process;
- the ability to be competitive and demanding in a team while being able to understand a colleague's point of view, etc.

The above-mentioned symptoms primarily predetermine the teacher's pedagogical views, which determine whether or not this teacher can implement innovative activity directed at the student's personality.

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To sum up, a reliable means of checking the implementation of innovative editorial activity of a future elementary school teacher focused on the individual and personal relationships is innovative actions in editorial situations and processes. The innovative ability of the future elementary school teacher is his theoretical, practical and psychological-physiological level of mastering the full content of educational innovation in the conditions of continuous education. As a result of this outstanding editorial system, it is necessary to ensure the unity of theory and practice, to educate students to conscientiously treat their studies and to develop creative activity, to form a whole set of knowledge and skills in specific subjects and types of general professional activities. should help.

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